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**Coronavirus age-dependent fatality:
a cautionary evolutionary reason why children should be out of school**

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Viruses have an outstanding ability to jump across species and evolve (Geoghehan, Duchêne & Holmes, 2017). Coronavirus is no exception. In November 2019, a strain of SARS-CoV-2 made a drastic host transition from a wild animal, probably a bat, to a single human (Zhu et al., 2020; Lu et al., 2020). In a few months, SARS-CoV-2 crossed the world, demonstrating its enormous ability to infect humans from different sex and ages (The Novel Coronavirus Pneumonia Emergency Response Epidemiology Team, 2020). It's fatality effects, however, are more constrained, killing older people in a higher rate than younger ones, as in China, where the pandemic started (The Novel Coronavirus Pneumonia Emergency Response Epidemiology Team, 2020). So far, despite children can be infected, they have shown very mild clinical manifestations (Shen et al. 2020). Here, I would like to point out that this fatality age-structure should not be assumed to be stationary and we should be open to the hypothesis that, given the conditions, SARS-CoV-2 could eventually evolve to attack more efficiently younger people, making the world pandemic even more profound. I argue that withdrawing kids and younger people from schools and Universities and leaving them at home is the proper procedure to decrease the chance of such undesirable adaptive shift becomes a reality.

The fatality age structure of a disease is a key parameter for the understanding of its impact on society (Fig. 1). Most common influenza virus kills young children at a high rate, reaches its minimum death rate around 10 years old to increase progressively towards elderly people (Reichert, Chowell & McCullers, 2012). The H1N1 virus which

caused the flu in 2018, killing dozens of millions around the globe, was atypical, with an extra fatality mode around 28 years-old (Gagnon et al., 2013). The SARS-CoV, which spread in 2003, had a death age-structure biased towards the elders (WHO, 2020). It's fatality rate was less than 1% for those younger than 24 years old, 6% for the 25-44 years range, 15% for those aged 45 to 64 years, and greater than 50% for older people. In mainland China, where the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic started, it killed <0.01% of children and teenagers, <0.1% for those in the 20-39 years old range, <1% for 40-59 years old, 1.93% for 60-69, 4.28% for 70-79, and 7.8% for people with more than 80 years old (values estimated by Verity et al., 2020). From an epidemiological view point, we should follow closely how the fatality age structure change across countries and through time.

Figure 1. Fatality age structure of some well-known flu. Curves are just illustrative.

The age structure of the population is another important parameter to predict how SARS-CoV-2 will impact different countries (Imai et al., 2020). Many developed nations have a relatively even age structure, with a larger proportion of the population in advanced age. In Italy, for instance, only 23% have 24 years or less while more than

20% of the population is over 65 years old (CIA, 2020). Based on such age structure pattern and the known fatality age structure, one is able to predict that such countries can potentially suffer heavy burdens with Covid-19. In most developing countries, in contrast, the age structure is triangular, with many more youngsters than elders. In Brazil, for instance, only 8.6% of the population has more than 65 years old while 38% is younger than 24 years (CIA, 2020). In such countries, everything else being equal, the projected number of deaths is expected to be proportionally lower, due to the fact that a great share of the young population is assumed to have a relatively low mortality risk.

It is still relatively early, however, to assume that the fatality age-structure of SARS-CoV-2 is a constant. SARS-CoV-2 RNA genome is changing continuously due to random mutations (Wang et al., 2020). Most of the such mutations will have no significant effect on the virus fitness and on our lives. Many will, in fact, jeopardize its functioning and will eventually be eliminated by natural selection. Mutations that increase the virus fitness are mostly probably complex and unlikely (Grubaugh, Petrone & Holmes, 2020), however, despite improbable, any mutant able to disperse more, reproduce quicker, and infest more efficiently the hosts, will be under strong selective advantage in an exponentially growing population. The fatality age structure of Covid-19 suggests that SARS-CoV-2 has difficulties in building high virulence loads in younger individuals, probably reducing transmission efficiency. The reasons for that are still unknown (Shen et al., 2020), but immunological barriers can eventually be surpassed, given the right conditions and enough evolutionary opportunities. In a world population with a triangular age structure, the emergence of a mutant able to build higher virus load on younger individuals could have an important effect on fatality rates.

I would like to hypothesize that different quarantine procedures can provide very different opportunities for SARS-CoV-2 to adapt to use younger hosts. The “Business as Usual” quarantine scenario provides a fertile ground for SARS-CoV-2 get adapted towards younger people (Fig. 2, left). In this scenario, schools and Universities remain open and, during the day, the virus has plenty of opportunities for kid-to-kid transmission. During the night, kid-to-kid transmission also take place due to the possibility of infected kids transmit the virus to their brothers and sisters; some in pre-school age. In this scenario, if a mutant emerges that is able to increase the virotic load

in younger people, this mutant will find plenty of opportunities to spread kid-to-kid 24-hours around the clock and gain adaptive advantage over the normal type in the younger population. Schools and Universities, then, can be the perfect medium where kid-adapted mutants emerge and spread. It should be highlighted that in the business as usual scenario, the dynamics associated to the adult-to-adult and adult-to-kid transmission still remain in place.

Figure 2. Epidemiological dynamics of SARS-CoV-2 under two distinct quarantine scenarios: Business as usual (left) and kids at home (right). Each scenario represents the spatial distribution of adults (squares) and children (circle) during day (top) and night (bottom) time. White filling represents uninfected individuals, black filling represents individuals infected by the normal virus type, and grey filling represent individuals infected by the kid-adapted mutant. In both scenarios people can be at school, work and home. Notice that in the Business as usual scenario, kid-to-kid transmission occurs uninterruptedly during day and night, while in the Kids at Home scenario the kid to kid transmission is rare.

In the “Kids at Home” scenario, the epidemiological dynamic changes considerably, with the imposition of a strong barrier for the evolution of kid-adapted mutants (Fig. 2, right). In this scenario, only part of the adult population remains active in their work, while children, their older siblings, and at least one adult stay at home. Under such circumstances, adult-to-adult is the main mode of transmission during the day, transferring the normal SARS-CoV-2 type. During the night, the normal virus type

can be transmitted to the co-habitant adults or even to kids. However, the emergence of a kid-adapted mutant is much less likely. And, if it does emerge, there is a reasonable chance of this mutant going extinct, since it can spread only locally to brothers and sisters and, after a while, they can become immune. If an adult is infected with this kid-adapted mutant, at the work it needs to be transferred to another adult before reaching another home. Thus, the “Kids at home” scenario is a less fertile ground for the emergence and propagation of a kid-adapted-mutant.

Worldwide, several different quarantine measures have been proposed to halt the expansion of SARS-CoV-2, some of them with very distinct effectiveness (Ferguson et al. 2020). In practice, some countries were simply unable to enforce quarantine procedures and SARS-CoV-2 is spreading unattended in a scenario similar to “business as usual”. Others, like Sweden, were leaving to the citizens’ conscience quarantine actions, and schools and Universities remained opened. In Brazil, after schools and Universities were closed, the President defended publicly that they can already go back to normal. In other countries, more restrict quarantine rules were imposed, including several combinations of actions, such as isolating just symptomatic cases and their family, isolating elder people, isolating part of the population or most of it. The World Health Organization (WHO) already suggest that kids should stay at home, since they can acquire the normal SARS-CoV-2 virus at school and transfer it to their parents and grandparents when going back home. This hypothetical work proposes that, despite the mortality rate of kids and young adults being relatively low, evolutionary scenarios suggest that quarantine of kids and young people can be much more significant in the long run than presently suspected. In summary, as a cautionary measure, kids and young adults should stay at home.

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